

MECHANISMS OF INFLUENCE OF THE GLOBAL INTERNET NETWORK ON THE FORMATION OF YOUTH LEGAL CULTURE

Yuldashev Shokhruh Ilkhomjon ugli

Basic doctoral student of the Department of Sociology
At National University of Uzbekistan named after Mirzo Ulugbek
Zip code 100174, Universitet Str. 4
E-mail: shohruh.yoldashev.97@mail.ru
<https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10460647>

ARTICLE INFO

Received: 29th December 2023
Accepted: 04th January 2024
Online: 05th January 2024

KEY WORDS

Legal culture, socialization, bringing legal culture to a new level, legal consciousness, changing the legal form, global, Internet, constituent documents, state youth law, youth culture.

ABSTRACT

In this article, the author analyzed the socialization of young people from a theoretical and practical point of view, and studied the opinions of legal scholars regarding changing the legal culture of young people. is a source of information that provides clear, simple, and fluent information about abstract concepts. Of course, the number of people in need of this factor is increasing day by day.

The global Internet is the only popular computer network in demand today, and it is a source of information that provides us with open, simple and fluent information about the uncertainty of all fields, that is, concepts that are abstract to our minds.

Of course, the number of people who need this factor is increasing day by day. This network is a global network worldwide. Because, although the matins informing about the available news, image and sound services and a number of possibilities are creating great relief on all fronts, on the other hand, they are involuntarily attracting humanity to the virtual world. Especially teenagers are not absent from this sphere of influence. In this regard, the words of experts prove the following results:

It is obvious that the positivity of the Internet leads to the all-round convenience and saving of the relevant amount of time in having important concrete evidences related to the science, field and activity of a person, but due to curiosity, they are overly addicted to excessive information on the Internet.

Inquisitiveness, mental development, observation, analytical ability and memory are causing a decrease in sharpness level. It is known that the use of the Internet tool is not obligatory for anyone, and it should be based on the law and the rules of the person's own thinking, as well as the standard requirements, that is, the correct selection of information from the Internet network. is appropriate. It can be seen that the scale of information contained in this network tool is so wide and numerous that it sometimes makes it difficult for us to extract the information we need. As we all know, the role of the search engine is invaluable for our work on the Internet. You can write all the information you need in the "search" box of such a site and choose the one you need from among the many information

that is released, or if you remember the address of a certain site, the same search again. You type in the keywords related to the site that the system will help you with, and you will see that site appear in front of you. There are other search engines on the Internet: Yahoo, Google, Ref.uz, etc. When giving a detailed and general description of the above search programs, it is appropriate to explain them through a system, for example, the Google system. This company is the leading search engine on the Internet, and seven out of ten Internet users around the world turn to this site in order to find this or that information. The system receives about 50 million requests every day, indexing eight billion web pages. It can search for information in 101 languages. In the following years, the Google system, which has become widely popular among Internet users all over the world, was launched in September 1998. Currently, in addition to search engines, this company has a number of other useful and convenient services, and their number is increasing. In fact, on the one hand, it is gratifying that not only the Internet has been created, but on the one hand, it is gratifying that such globally developing information technologies have a positive influence on the young generation, but on the other hand, in order to protect them from various negative lessons. encourages the strengthening of the educational environment.

Today, military personnel receive colorful information and information through media such as radio-television, press, and the Internet.

In such a situation, where the global information space is expanding more and more, it is no doubt necessary to protect the minds of our soldiers, to educate them one-sidedly so that they do not read it and do not see it, and to surround them with an iron wall. doesn't fit. Why, we have set ourselves the task of building an open and free democratic society in our country, and we will never turn back from this path. Therefore, we imagine the future of our country not wrapped in our own shell, but with deep absorption of universal and democratic values. Using the experience of developed countries, we see the liberalization of the state and society in the wider implementation of human rights and freedoms, the diversity of ideas in our lives. We are supporters of mutually beneficial cooperation with the entire enlightened international community for a peaceful, free and prosperous life.

Based on the wide possibilities of the modern information system, it can be said that it is necessary to create a management mechanism for obtaining, storing, using and distributing information in Uzbekistan from the point of view of common interest and common development, as well as a deep understanding of its essence and elements. Based on this vital need, we consider it necessary to apply the following methods of creating a system of ensuring national security in the information sector:

First, the sociological direction. Based on the role of the information of the development of the society as a social reality in the process of obtaining and distributing information, it is necessary to study the level of social thinking and its currents. It is necessary to determine the way of thinking based on different strata of the population, views, professional and other social situations.

Second, the statistical direction. In a multi-ethnic country, especially in Uzbekistan, where more than 130 nationalities and peoples live, about 20 religious denominations are active, inter-ethnic and inter-religious conflicts can arise under the influence of various

political interests and destructive ideas. to study the sources, to have an accurate account in this regard - to have analytical solutions to the books.

Third, political conflictology and political psychology. At a time when information is becoming a psychological threat, in a situation where various destructive ideas have their influence on the human mind and thinking, it is necessary to study the sources of political conflicts, to determine the factors, and to determine the political views and mentality. , socio-political and psychological should be studied consistently.

Fourth, logical systemic and functional analysis. The information system, in particular, the psychological impact of information should be evaluated as an important part of the information policy system and tool. It is necessary to approach reality in this way and draw scientific-analytical theoretical and practical conclusions. Social opinion formed under the influence of information flow in a dense information society should be consistently studied from the point of view of science.

Fifth, the priority of the idea of national independence in the information system. In the process of choosing a "product" from the information base of any citizen, ensuring priority of ideological immunity in his heart, spirit, mood, character, behavior and attitude as a consequence of all this. Of course, during the 23 years of Uzbekistan's independence, serious changes took place in the field of mass information communication. First of all, every citizen's freedom of speech and opinion, the right to receive and distribute information is guaranteed by the Constitution. A number of media laws have been created and are being implemented. The number of independent publications has increased dramatically. All this indicates the unique development of the national information system in the internal life of the country. It should also be noted that it is becoming clear that not all of the information and data available on the Internet are real. Based on this, it can be said that it is appropriate to consciously observe the accuracy of the received evidence. Only then can we be sure that the knowledge we acquire through the Internet will have a positive effect in our lives. In short, in order not to create a void in the spiritual world of our servicemen, we must always form a sense of respect for the national and national values of a healthy way of life in their hearts and minds. It should not be forgotten that today even a small message, which at first glance seems to be insignificant, directed against human spirituality, takes strength from the intensity of globalization in the world of information and causes great damage, which is invisible, but the damage cannot be compensated by anything. possible.

References:

1. O'zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidentining "O'zbekiston Respublikasi oliy ta'lim tizimini 2030 yilgacha rivojlantirish konsepsiyasini tasdiqlash to'g'risida"gi 2019 yil 8 oktabrdagi PF-5847-son Farmoni.
2. O'zbekiston Respublikasi Ichki Ishlar vazirligi U. Tadjixanov, A. Saidov "Xukukiy madaniyat nazariyasi" Ikki tomli, 2-tom. 1998 y.
3. Saidov A. Zamonaviy konstitutsionalizm: Milliy va xorijiy tajriba // <https://xs.uz/uzkr/post/zamonavijkonstitutsionalizm-millij-va-khorizhij-tazhriba>

4. O'zbekiston Respublikasi Oliy Majlisi Senatining 2022-yil 4-fevraldagi SQ-479-IV-sonli qarori.
5. www.lex.uz – O'zbekiston Respublikasi milliy qonunlar bazasi, Adliya vazirligi sayti.
6. www.minjust.uz – O'zbekiston Respublikasi Adliya vazirligi rasmiy sayti.
7. www.uza.uz – O'zbekiston milliy axborot agentligi.
8. www.pfru.uz – Respublika tibbiy ijtimoiy ekspertiza inspeksiyasi.